

The Dialogue between Reason and Intuition in Contemporary Philosophy

Noichl, Maximilian

noichlmax@hotmail.co.uk

Utrecht University, Niederlande

ORCID: 0000-0003-4518-0837

DeDeo, Simon

sdedeo@andrew.cmu.edu

Carnegie Mellon University, Vereinigte Staaten von Amerika

Introduction

Where does philosophical progress come from? It is natural to see philosophical thought as a back-and-forth between intuition-building examples and more logically-watertight and universal positions (see, e.g., Cekiera, 2024) — a view of the philosophical dialectic that can be found in Rawls' notion of reflective equilibrium and, in its general form, is at least as old as the *Parmenides* of Plato. But how does this back-and-forth lead to the exploration of new areas of the cultural landscape? Do philosophers construct examples to make sense of their positions or, conversely, do they take new positions in response to the novel intuitions provided by a thought experiment? Can new positions emerge solely from the argument-based development of earlier ones, or do they require support from intuition that only examples can provide? Philosophical discourse, building logical arguments in tandem with articulating and refining intuitions, provides a compelling test-bed for new theories of intellectual development that go beyond studies of novelty in the empirical sciences (Wu et al., 2019), popular culture (Jing et al., 2025), or political debate (Barron et al, 2018) to see how the new can emerge from the dialectic of reason and imagination.

Objectives

We draw on the novel capabilities of contemporary Large Language Models (LLMs) to study the progress of philosophical thought. These LLMs, with appropriate prompt engineering, can answer, at scale, questions that used to require extensive human coding. Importantly for our research questions, they allow us to extract, from tens of thousands of papers, two aspects of the philosophical dialectic,

example-making and position-articulation. Combined with novel methods from network science, this makes it possible to visualize how these two modes interact with each other both at the level of an individual reasoner and the cultural evolution of this reason-making over long timescales.

We can look, first, at how examples and positions are combined within a single paper; this allows us to see not only how the famous examples and positions of philosophy (variants of Descartes' "evil demon", say, or forms of utilitarianism) are used and re-used, but also the long-tail of non-starter examples and positions that fail to gain wide currency. Our methods also allow us to look at life histories of both examples and positions, which appear to rise and fall with characteristic timescales.

With these basic results in hand, we can then provide a first answer for our core research question: when an example and a position are linked by a critical number of philosophers, which comes first: the example, the position, or the linkage? Does a long standing example become connected to more recent position (an intuition-first outcome), or vice versa, with a long-standing position receiving support from a more recently-born example? When are examples most fertile — do they tend to connect to new positions early in their history, or does it take time for them to be understood? Similarly for positions: do philosophers connect a position to examples early on, in order to give them intuitive substance, or do examples come later, nearer the end of a position's time of flourishing, as philosophers attempt to go beyond the confines of argument?

Dataset

The data for this project consists of a representative sample drawn from all philosophical articles archived on JSTOR, evenly distributed across the period from 1950 to 2015, covering a comprehensive range of recent English-language philosophy. Our dataset was constructed to sample the years uniformly, with 350 papers per year, for a total of 23,100 papers overall; the uniform sampling ensures that the increase in publications over time does not lead us to overfit to more recent years.

Using GPT-4o, the dataset was systematically annotated for core structures of philosophical reasoning, specifically rigorous cognitive devices such as philosophical arguments, positions ('positions') and intuition-building components such as illustrative examples, metaphors, and thought experiments ('examples').

Methods

The full texts were fed to the LLM in batches of roughly 3 pages, which was prompted to excerpt brief passages corresponding to either examples or positions. The LLM annotated these excerpts with brief titles; e.g., "scientific realism" or "mind-body-dualism" (positions); "the movement of billiard balls" or "Hempel's ravens" (examples). Titles

are useful for readability, but couldn't be used to merge excerpts into more general types, because (1) small variations in title choice prevent us from merging things that should be merged, and (2) distinct cases can end up with very similar titles.

To merge candidates, we identified "nearby" excerpt candidates using a custom philosophy-fine-tuned modern-BERT (Warner et al. 2024; Reimers & Gurevych 2019) model. The merging candidates were then passed to GPT-4o, which decided, based on the surrounding texts, whether two candidate excerpts referred to the "same" entity. This process was repeated for the seven nearest neighbours to each excerpts, when we registered very few new merges. This process produces a network, where examples (and positions, respectively) are connected to each other. We then used eigenvector centrality to determine a set of "canonical" excerpts, defined as nodes that were relatively central to the networks in which they appear, and we assigned other excerpts to these canonical examples on the basis of a random walk model.

This method corresponds to a simple cognitive model where examples and positions are linked together on the basis of mental association: two examples are more likely to fall under the same category if they are nearby in the underlying similarity network — if one can get from example A to example B by following a short and robust chain of steps involving intermediate examples that are effectively "the same".

Fig. 1: The "bent stick illusion" example cluster; each node corresponds to a particular excerpt from a paper, while edges between nodes represent judgements by the LLM that two excerpts are "the same". A central node (here, "Perceptual Illusion of a Stick in Water") corresponds to the canonical example for this cluster. Only the nodes that lead into the canonical example are shown; other nodes in the network, including some connected to nodes here, lead more directly into different canonical examples, and are associated with different clusters.

An example of this merging step is illustrated in Figure 1, which shows a set of excerpted examples from different papers that were merged together into a single example: roughly, how the refraction of light in water leads a straight object to appear, contrary to fact, to be straight. The canonical example is "Perceptual Illusion of a Stick in Water" and one can see how, for example, the merging process connects this to both very minor variations such as "half-submerged stick", and related examples such as "moon following travelers" and "perception of depth in a mirror".

Fig 2. A view of the philosophical landscape implicit in the position/example-structure. a) shows a UMAP-dimensionality reduction (McInnes et al., 2018), in which each datapoint represents one position or example, arranged closer or further away from others according to the Jaccard-similarity of their co-occurrence-patterns. The resulting clusters correspond to discursive streams in which positions and examples interplay. One of these, epistemology, is illustrated with its largest examples and positions in b). A single pair of an example co-evolving with a position is shown in c).

With these merged examples and positions in hand, we can then study the characteristic life histories of these larger clusters. Figure 2 (b) shows a subset of our data, sorted by modal year; positions (in red) have a median lifetime of 22 years, while examples have a median lifetime of 26.

In addition, we can study how a position and example pair come to be linked over time. Figure 2(c) shows a particular example of one of our pairs: the linkage between the example "evil demon world", and the position "epistemic externalism". The first instance of the example (in our data) comes much earlier than the first instance of the position: "evil demon world" first appears in 1958, while epistemic externalism appears first more than twenty years later, in 1979. The first shared paper, i.e., the first paper to include both the example and the position in our data, appears in 1986. After this point, evil demon world appears increasingly linked to epistemic externalism — a case of joint flourishing where after 2000, for example, the majority of papers that use the example also contain the epistemic externalism position, and vice versa.

Microdynamics like these link together examples and positions into a vast bipartite network, where an edge between a position and an example represents the co-occurrence of the pair in at least two papers. This dataset, combined with temporal data on the introduction of examples and positions, and citation data, offers a unique perspective into the flow of philosophical reasoning as a collective cognitive process.

Figure 2 shows the relative effect on future citations of (1) being the first to introduce a position or (2) example; (3) being the first to introduce a position-position connection, (4) example-example connection, or (5) position-example connection; (6) including multiple positions, or (7) examples. Being the first to introduce either a position or an example always helps, but being the first to introduce a position has a far more powerful effect — philosophy reward the new-position taker more than the new-example giver. The opposite is true for the effect of including multiple instances: while citations are preferentially awarded to diverse papers, the effect is larger for including a diversity of examples. Informally, philosophers value new positions more, but they also value the intuition-building of examples.

Intriguingly, there seems to be a penalty for novel *connections*: being the first to connect two positions together (or two examples, or a position-example pair) seems to *hurt* future citations. One way to make sense of this reversal (it is good to introduce a new position, but harmful to introduce a new connection) is by saying that while there are an enormous number of possible connections to make, only a very small number of them are actually fruitful. Most new attempts at drawing a connection fail, simply because there are strong underlying affinities.

Fig. 3 Model Coefficients for a linear model predicting log-citation-counts from example/position data with fixed effects for journal of publication $F(153, 12537) = 31.45, p < .001, R^2 = 0.277, \text{adj. } R^2 = 0.269. N = 12691.$ Coefficients for journals are not shown.

Discussion

This work presents a first attempt at making sense of a basic feature of philosophical reasoning: the coexistence, and coevolution, of examples (specific, concrete pieces of "evidence", albeit often a priori in form) and positions (general beliefs, supported by argument, about how things are). Our work allows us both to zoom in on particular cases of how examples and positions emerge and are later linked together, and to study how the sum total of these individual processes combine to produce large scale effects on philosophical culture.

While we have focused here on a simple proxy for philosophical attention — the citation count — the underlying data can allow us to examine basic questions in how philosophers create new positions, how they do, or do not, rely on examples to illustrate them. Philosophy is more than just the simple statement of positions, and this work provides the first systematic study, from a digital humanities perspective, of how positions and examples link up to produce recognizably "philosophical" work.

Our methodology, currently, also has limitations. Both co-authors spent a great deal of time reading samples from the data to ensure (1) that examples and positions that were extracted deserved to be so called, and (2) that the merging process produced sensible results—that it did not, for example, merge things that ought to remain distinct. However, it would be better to conduct a more formal evaluation of the quality of our LLM annotations; we are currently in the process of getting ethics clearance to validate our categorizations using a subject pool of professional philosophers at Carnegie Mellon University.

Bibliography

Barron, A. T., Huang, J., Spang, R. L., & DeDeo, S. 2018. Individuals, institutions, and innovation in the debates of the French Revolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(18), 4607-4612.

Cekiera, K. 2024. Intuition as a Source of Evidence in Philosophy: The Minimal View. *Revista de Humanidades de Valparaíso*, (24), 9-24.

Jing, E., DeDeo, S., Wright, D. R., & Ahn, Y. Y. 2025. 'Sameness entices, but novelty enchants in fanfiction online'. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 12(1), 1-10.

McInnes, Leland, John Healy, and James Melville. 2018. "UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.03426> .

Reimers, Nils, and Iryna Gurevych. 2019. "Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings Using Siamese BERT-Networks." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10084*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1908.10084> .

Warner, Benjamin, Antoine Chaffin, Benjamin Clavié, et al. 2024. 'Smarter, Better, Faster, Longer: A Modern Bidirectional Encoder for Fast, Memory Efficient, and Long Context Finetuning and Inference'. *arXiv:2412.13663*. Preprint, arXiv, December 19. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2412.13663> .

Wu, L., Wang, D., & Evans, J. A. 2019. Large teams develop and small teams disrupt science and technology. *Nature*, 566(7744), 378-382.